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*Comparative analysis of linguistic and culturological
phenomena of uzbek and English people*

Annotation

This article is dedicated to comparative analysis of linguistic and culturological phenomena of English and uzbek people in general.

The aim of the article is to study the national-cultural comparative analysis of linguistic and culturological phenomena of English and Uzbek languages by comparing and learning and knowing the main and crucial differences between each other.

Keywords: cultural, linguistic, linguacultural, comparative, national, crucial, specificity, reality, phenomena.

Speech culture and the art of public speaking are the issues that were conducted constantly and still supposed to be studied in the world linguistics. The most essential ability to understand the characteristics of learning foreign languages is to learn how to communicate with people of different nationalities and, most importantly, to enjoy this communication. The language of each ethnic group is a living organism and is inextricably linked with its history, culture and social life. The problem of the interaction of language and culture is one of the central issues in linguistics. This article is based on the analysis of linguistic and cultural stereotypes in the Uzbek and English languages, as well as the prevention of intercultural conflict. The problem of the interaction of language and culture is one of the central issues in linguistics. English people grow up in their “European Dream”, the equality of opportunity and

competition, material wealth and self-reliance, among which self-reliance is emphasized. Therefore, there are many words with the prefix “self-”, such as “self-evident, self-acting, self-assumed, self-care, self-study...” a long list of “-self” words with the similar connotation of “being oneself”, i.e., the individualism. The individualism can be seen nearly in every aspect of life. The English build their country, to coast the territory and to gain the independence. Among the nonverbal conversation, kinesics is the main type that every part of the human body can convey information. It includes visual behavior, tactile behavior, olfactic behavior, posture, gesture, facial expression, and so on. In terms of kinesics, English and Uzbek behave differently. For these behaviors are unconsciously acquired through culture.

(1) For example, “tongue out”

E—English use this act to show contempt.

U— the Uzbeks use it to show their shock.

“Crossed legs”

E—English men like to cross their legs to be at ease.

U—Uzbek generally consider it as impolite to the guests.

(2) “Visual behavior”

U—English regard direct eye-contact as being honest,

attention. In communication, The British always use eyecontact to show the interests in the topic, but not stare in an invariable, constant way of course. This conveys that “I am listening to you, but not getting into your privacy”, and “I am equal to you”.

U—The English way may seem quite rude to the Uzbek. Uzbek people do not look into other’s eyes always, for it may cause unrest, awkwardness, or even offense.

(3) “Facial expression”

When people are born, they carry out the first expression—crying. When cries, everybody shows his lips downward, no matter whether he is Uzbek or English. It is no different, for facial expressions are genetic. People, from any place, show cries, smiles, angers, etc., in much the same way. But considering different cultures, people may carry different facial expressions toward the same object or event. That is decided

by different cultures. The explanation can be illustrated by being encountering the word “running dog”.

U—English may smile for their love of pet dogs.

U—It may arouse contempt, or anger in the Uzbek, or may even a spit at it. There is an experiment to show this difference. Two movies, one of which is amusing, the other being repulsive, are shown to Asian and English students. expression changes may occur within this personal distance.

(3) Social distance.

It is also called “politeness distance”, at which most common communication or deal-making occur. It’s at arm’s length that is 4-12 feet, which is a safe distance. People may hear each other even in a low voice, but cannot discover the slight changes of facial expressions. And talk at this distance is mostly formal.

(4) Public distance.

This is a communicative distance of 12-25 feet in much more formal situation. Talking at this distance should not be in a low voice or whisper.

(5) Long distance.

This is a public communication distance of 25 feet or more a public speech is addressed. People communicate with different distance in accordance with respective culture. In Uzbekistan, people would like to narrow down the distance to show warmth and intimacy. Two young girls may take a walk hand in hand or arm in arm much within the intimacy distance, which may shock the English as homosexuals. In England, two friends do not walk much into the intimacy distance. Everyone has a distance, a boundary. They keep this even in queues. They may be stunned in the pushing and shoving in the Uzbek queue for a seat in the library. Anyway, it is the condition and situation form the habitation. Families with the exception of using sen/you (singular) for little siblings. However, among friends sen/you (singular) is more accepted if they know each other for a long time. Whereas in English, there is no such pronoun to show respect to people, because in both singular and plural, there is one pronoun that is “you” and they use it in all situations. The usage of honorifics in English, such as Mr. Mrs. Ms. before the surname of the person is still in a trend in

some situations, but nowadays people prefer to call each other with their first name regardless their age and social status. In Uzbek culture, however, there is not these kinds of honorifics, instead, in a very formal situation; there used the first name of the person plus the middle name which remained from Russian culture, for instance, (Anvar Rajabovich) for males plus the inflectional morpheme (-ich) and for females it is (-(o)vna) like in (Dilnoza Zokirovna). We have also a pure Uzbek version of this, like to add the father's name of the person according to their gender, like in "Dilnoza Zokir qizi" means (Dilnoza Zokir's daughter) or "Anvar Rajab o`g`li" means (Anvar Rajab's son). In Uzbek culture, the following expressions are used for addressing. "Ustoz" used for addressing to teachers, uncle (amaki) used for brother of father side, uncle (tog'a) used to address mother's brother; and grandmother (buvi), grandfather (buva/bobo), aunt (xola) if it is the sibling of mother side, and aunt (amma) if it is the sibling of father side. In other cases, although people do not know each other very well, they call elder females opa [opa] or elder males aka [aka] for showing respect to their age. At least, we should use "opa" or "aka" via adding it to the name of the person, like in (Dilnoza opa) or (Anvar aka) if we want to seem polite for Uzbek people. One of the other utmost features in Uzbek culture is that from ancient time, wives never addressed to their husband with their names, instead they used the word "begim" [begim] means "my dear husband". As you you can see examples above, we have ample differences in our culturology and we have a different mentality than English human beings. We are living in Uzbekistan and we have pride, prejudice, wisdom, love for the country are intensively powerful and we are called Asians and English people have another kind of mentality and they are europeans.

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